

The presence of an emergency preparedness within the country of Bulgaria and its impact on the energy vulnerability due to natural disasters.

Author: Irena Stanislavova Shaleva

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Keywords

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Executive Summary

The Data Governance Plan for Bulgaria aims to establish a strong groundwork to collect and analyse effectively the data from different areas within the country, differentiating between cities and villages to measure and manage energy access. The plan emphasizes the importance of accurate, accessible, and secure data in supporting national energy access goals, particularly in rural and urban electrification with particular attention on the presence.

Key Findings

The current national database lacks coordination between rural and urban areas within the country, leaving gaps in information that make the prediction and calculation of energy access incomplete. There's a need for a centralized database with a structural division between data stewards, owners, custodians and users. Strengthen the data governance framework with data quality standards, security protocols and regular audits on the emergency plan of each village and city within each area. Creating a focus group to compensate for the data gaps by collecting it and analysing it locally.

1. Introduction :

Purpose and Scope

This data governance plan will address the management of geospatial and energy-related data critical to electrification and disaster management in Bulgaria, with a focus on both pre-disaster preparedness and post-disaster response. The plan involves collaboration with national government organizations and United Nations agencies to ensure comprehensive data coverage, particularly for emergency preparedness. The plan will prioritize identifying and analyzing regions in Bulgaria that are most affected by energy isolation and climate-related natural disasters. It will also explore the overlap between these regions to pinpoint "energy-vulnerable" areas. In cases where such overlap does not exist, the plan will establish criteria to address the unique challenges of each area separately.

Objective and aims

The primary goal of this data governance plan is to improve the management and utilization of data related to Bulgaria's emergency preparedness and the impact of natural disasters on energy vulnerability. The plan will ensure that data is accurately collected, securely stored, and effectively used to inform decision-making processes.

The key objectives include:

1. **Assessment of existing emergency preparedness data:**

- Evaluate the current data on Bulgaria's emergency preparedness, distinguishing between data specific to urban and rural areas versus generalized data.

2. **Impact of natural disasters on energy vulnerability:**

- Gather and manage data on the effects of climate-related disasters on the energy grid.
- Identify and categorize regions isolated from the energy grid due to these disasters, defining these as "energy-vulnerable" areas.

3. **Post-Disaster data management:**

- Track and assess data on the aftermath of natural disasters and their impact on energy infrastructure.

4. Implementation and Monitoring of Emergency Plans:

- Use data to evaluate the effectiveness and implementation of emergency preparedness plans.
- Continuously update and refine data governance practices to adapt to the evolving needs of disaster response and energy management.

2. Methodology

Modelling Approach/Tool Implemented

The data governance framework is designed to support energy access modelling using tools such as QGIS, which requires high-quality geospatial and demographic data. This tool helps to simulate various scenarios for rural electrification and clean cooking initiatives.

The database will follow a relational model with tables for population data, energy infrastructure, and resource availability, linked through unique identifiers for each geographical region

The above data is part of an entity-attribute database with a one-to-many relationship, to get the results we expect the information will be analysed as follows:

- The goal is to obtain the differentiation between the areas connected to the electric system and the ones that are not, to draw the line between the two categories there needs to be the value of the energy consumption for the building in that area.
- As in the previous case, observation of areas connected with their energy consumption refers to buildings with energy access to the grid.
- Electricity consumption can be done using the type of connection (solar/diesel hybrid or solar PV with battery storage), its nominal capacity (in kW), and the number of customers served.
- Examine which city and villages within an area have emergency plans (by checking if the village or city has an updated emergency procedure and if the

area where the city or village is located is affected by natural disasters with a certain frequency.

- The impact of a natural disaster occurring on an area can be calculated by putting in proportion the characteristics of the natural disaster with the area affected and the presence of an emergency plan to prevent the increased cost of impact.
- Measurement of the area affected and if it has an emergency plan will need the cost of the impact and the presence of a before and after plan.
- Comparison between the initial measurement of the areas containing cities and villages and putting them about the areas that are affected by natural disasters and missing an emergency plan, check if they are the same or if we need a new category of isolated areas without energy access due to natural calamity

The database will follow a relational model with tables for “Area”, “Building”, “Emergency Plan”, “Energy Access”, “System”, “Area Affected”, “NaturalDisaster” linked through unique identifiers.

With a series of one-to-many relations. Access to the energy database will be tiered, with government officials granted editing rights, while external researchers are provided with read-only access under strict data-sharing agreements.

The criteria for data collection methodology is characterized by the following criteria: Quality, Accuracy, Relevance, Validity, Reliability, Bias Reduction, Informed Decision-making, and Achievement of Research Objectives. Data will be collected using GPS-enabled mobile devices during field surveys in rural areas, complemented by satellite imagery from Sentinel-2 for remote regions.

Below can be found an overview of the various types of data collection methods with their functionality and examples of software used.

Data will undergo a multi-step cleaning process, including outlier detection and consistency checks, with a focus on avoiding repetition and maintaining the logical relationship between the values. Regarding the standardisation follow the procedures standardising data formats, units of measurement and coordinating of system. Finally

for the procedure of validation use methods like cross-referencing against government census data.

Geospatial data from satellite imagery will be integrated with demographic data using a common spatial reference system, enabling comprehensive energy access mapping.

All sensitive data will be encrypted using AES-256 encryption, and access will be controlled via role-based permissions with regular audits to ensure compliance. Encryption keys will be managed centrally by the IT department, with strict protocols in place to prevent unauthorised access.

A risk assessment identified the potential for data breaches as a significant threat, particularly during data transmission over public networks. Risks will be divided depending on their impact and according to the degree, the mitigation strategy will be applied accordingly.

Risk	Impact	Mitigation Strategy
Unauthorised Access	High	Implement strong access controls, authentication mechanisms, and regular access reviews
Data Breaches	Medium	Encrypt data at rest and in transit, and monitor for unusual activity.
Insider Threats	High	Limit access based on roles, conduct security awareness training, and monitor user behaviour.
Malware and Ransomware	High	Regularly update antivirus software, educate users about phishing, and maintain backups.
Physical Security Risks	High	Secure physical access points and use encryption on portable devices.
Third-Party Risks	High	Assess third-party security practices and sign data protection agreements.

Energy access data will be made available under a Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International License, allowing free use for non-commercial purposes

Data will be published quarterly on the national energy data portal in both CSV and GeoJSON formats, ensuring accessibility for both technical and non-technical users.

All geospatial data will be documented according to ISO 19115 standards, including detailed descriptions of data sources, methods, and accuracy

A version control system will be implemented to track all changes to datasets, ensuring that updates are logged, and older versions can be accessed if necessary

Type of Data Collection Method	Description	Example
Survey Tools	Software applications are designed to collect quantitative data from a large audience through structured questionnaires.	QuestionPro, SurveyMonkey, Google Forms
Focus Group	Tools facilitate the collection of qualitative data through guided conversations and group discussions	Zoom, MS Team
Observation and Data Field Collection	Tools facilitate the collection of qualitative data through guided conversations and group discussions.	Open Data Kit, REDCap
Mobile Data Collection	Tools leverage smartphones and tablets to gather data on the go. These tools enable users to collect data offline and sync it when an internet connection is available.	KoboToolBox, SurveyCTO
Data Analysis Tools	Tools support various statistical methods and data visualisation	Tableau, SPSS

	techniques, allowing users to interpret data effectively and make informed decisions based on their findings.	
Qualitative Data Analysis	Tools are essential for analysing interview transcripts, open-ended survey responses, social media content, etc...	NVivo, Dedoose
General Data Collection and Management	Tools often include features for data integration, cleansing, and security, ensuring that data is accessible and usable for analysis across different departments and projects.	Airtable, Microsoft Excel

The Ministry of Energy will allocate an annual budget for database maintenance and updates, ensuring that data sets remain current and relevant

A dedicated team of data managers and IT specialists will be maintained, with funding secured through government grants and international partnerships.

An annual user survey will be conducted to gather feedback on data accessibility and quality, with findings used to inform improvements to the data governance framework

Quarterly training sessions will be offered to data stewards on the latest data management tools and techniques, with participants receiving certification upon completion.

Data sources

Primary data will be sourced by the Sociological Lead together with the Research Lead together with their respective teams through surveys, interviews and experiments, while secondary data will be obtained from Government Databases, Academic research, International Organisations and International energy datasets for example the

UNIDIR and the Bulgarian Ministry of Energy. In addition, Open Data Platforms such as OpenStreetMap and the databases from the World Bank will be considered as essential data sources.

Primary Data (Provided by Sociological Lead + Research Lead with their respective teams)	Secondary Data (Provided by Government Databases, Academic research and International Organisations)	Open Data Platforms (OpenStreetMap, World Bank databases, national geospatial data portals)
Survey	Bulgarian Federation of Industrial Energy Consumers	European Bank for Reconstruction and Development
Interviews	Bulgarian Independent Energy Exchange	European Investment Bank
Focus Groups	Energy and Water Regulatory Commission	European Regional Development Fund
Observations	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change	Energyinfo
Experiments	Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works	EM-DAT
Case studies	National Electricity Company	
Ethnography	National Statistical Institute	
	European strategic energy technology (SET) plan	
	UNIDIR	

Assumptions

The initial assumption is as follows: all areas with buildings that are isolated from the main city centres have no energy access, while populated areas are guaranteed to have connections with electric systems. A secondary assumption is centred on the fact that the

sole presence of a general emergency plan is enough to protect the city or village that is covered by it. It is up to the result of this report to prove whether the assumptions are correct or not by data collecting and data analysis.

3. Results

Charts and Graphs

Main findings of results

The analysis revealed that current data management practices are fragmented, with significant gaps in data quality and accessibility. For example, rural electrification data is often outdated or incomplete, leading to unreliable modelling outcomes.

Areas with outdated emergency plans that do not account for the frequency, location, and characteristics of natural disasters will be severely impacted, as their response and preventive measures will be inadequate for the growing energy access needs.

Attribute	Description	Data Type	Constraint
AreaID	Unique Identifier for the area	INT	NOT NULL
population	Number of population	INT	NOT NULL
location	Geometrical location for the area	GEOMETRY(point, 4326)	NOT NULL
postal_code_area	The number for postal code area	INT	NOT NULL
area_connected	Whether the area is connected or not	INT	NOT NULL
EmergencyPlanID	Unique Identifier for the Emergency Plan	INT	NOT NULL
area_type	Type of area (whether city or village)	TEXT	NOT NULL
BuildingID	Unique identifier for the Building	INT	NOT NULL
building_type	Type of building	TEXT	NOT NULL
number_abitants	Number of inhabitants per building	INT	NOT NULL
location_building	The area where the city is allocated with geometrical measurements	GEOMETRY(Point, 4326)	NOT NULL
EnergyAccessID	Unique Identifier for the energy access	INT	NOT NULL

energy_consumption	Energy consumption linked to the usage of electricity	INT	NOT NULL
customers_served	Number of customers served by the energy access	INT	NOT NULL
SystemID	Unique identifier for System	INT	NOT NULL
type_of_connection	Type of connection for energy access	TEXT	NOT NULL
voltage_capacity	Voltage capacity of electricity system	FLOAT	NOT NULL
preparation_plan	Emergency plan before natural disaster occurs	TEXT	NOT NULL
after_event_plan	Emergency plan after natural disaster occurs	TEXT	NOT NULL
cost_of_recovery	Cost of recovery from disaster	FLOAT	NOT NULL
NaturalDisasterID	Unique identifier for natural disaster	INT	NOT NULL
type_of_event	Type of natural disaster that has occurred	TEXT	NOT NULL
frequency	Frequency of event happening	INT	NOT NULL
AreaAffectedID	Unique Identifier for affected area	INT	NOT NULL
area_affected	Type of area affected by natural disaster	TEXT	NOT NULL

impact_cost	Cost of the impact	FLOAT	NOT NULL
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4. Discussion

Insights and results implications

When assessing areas in the country, the location of each village or city should be represented as a geometrical point. This point will indicate whether a building is connected to the electricity system and if it has an emergency plan. Each area contains at least one building, which is associated with a specific number of inhabitants, a unique energy access identifier, and its geographical coordinates. This unique identifier links the building to its energy consumption data and the customers served by that system. Each energy system has its ID, detailing the connected buildings, the type of connection, and the voltage capacity

The emergency plan for each building should include both preventive measures and post-event actions. By considering these factors, it is possible to estimate the recovery costs based on the damage caused by natural disasters, each identified by a unique ID. The type, frequency, and severity of the disaster also have specific identifiers. The affected area can be measured using polygon geometry, allowing for the calculation of economic impact and disaster frequency.

Areas with outdated emergency plans that do not account for the frequency, location, and characteristics of natural disasters will be severely impacted, as their response and preventive measures will be inadequate for the growing energy access needs.

Limitations of study

A key challenge may be the lack of comprehensive data for rural areas, the absence of an emergency plan and the usage of outdated and incomplete databases to make analyses and calculations.

Potential areas for future research

The potential areas for future research are the level of update of the present emergency plans and the cooperation on a local, national and international level between the municipalities and the infrastructure within a specific area to ensure a coordinated centre for emergency prevention, response and recovery.

5. Conclusion

Recap and lessons learnt

This data governance plan prioritizes energy access as a fundamental need across Bulgaria. It emphasizes the critical role of having updated and tailored emergency plans, not only for isolated rural areas but also for major cities. While rural regions may be more vulnerable to natural disasters, without effective prevention and active response measures, no area—urban or rural—can recover swiftly from the economic and physical damage inflicted by such events.

Recommendations

The missing data for the rural areas creates a gap in the governance plan, thus fixing the missing spots of information is necessary to have a complete overview of our challenge, which is areas in a country that are cut off from energy access.

References

Republic of Bulgaria Advisory Services on a National Climate Change Adaptation Strategy and Action Plan, n.d.

International Energy Agency (IEA). (n.d.) *Guidebook for Improved Electricity Access Statistics*. Available at:

<https://iea.blob.core.windows.net/assets/cc0ed3f6-84e5-465c-920c-62f2be286db1/GuidebookforImprovedElectricityAccessStatistics.pdf> [Accessed 21 Aug. 2024].

Republic of Bulgaria Ministry of Energy and Ministry of the Environment and Water. (n.d.) *Integrated Energy and Climate Plan of the Republic of Bulgaria 2021-2030*.

Available at:

https://energy.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-06/bg_final_necp_main_en_0.pdf

[Accessed 21 Aug. 2024].

Ghawana, T., Pashova, L. and Zlatanova, S. (2021) 'Geospatial Data Utilisation in National Disaster Management Frameworks and the Priorities of Multilateral Disaster Management Frameworks: Case Studies of India and Bulgaria', *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 10(9), p.610. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi10090610>.

World Bank Group. (n.d.) *Bulgaria Climate Risk Country Profile*. Available at:

https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/sites/default/files/2021-06/15848-WB_Bulgaria%20Country%20Profile-WEB.pdf [Accessed 21 Aug. 2024].

Trading Economics. (2024) 'Bulgaria | Climate Change | World Bank Development Indicators'. Available at:

<https://tradingeconomics.com/bulgaria/indicators-wb-data.html?g=climate+change>

[Accessed 21 Aug. 2024].

Kafka, K. (2021) *Energo-Pro*. Available at: <https://www.energo-pro.com/en> [Accessed 21 Aug. 2024].

International Trade Administration. (2024) 'Bulgaria - Energy', *Country Commercial Guides*. Available at: <https://www.trade.gov/country-commercial-guides/bulgaria-energy> [Accessed 21 Aug. 2024].

Republic of Bulgaria Ministry of Energy. (n.d.) Available at:

https://energy.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-11/ener-2020-01182-00-00-en-tra-00_0.pdf [Accessed 21 Aug. 2024].

International Trade Administration. (2024) 'Bulgaria - Energy', *Country Commercial Guides*. Available at: <https://www.trade.gov/country-commercial-guides/bulgaria-energy> [Accessed 21 Aug. 2024].

